

NAME: Sindy Poppitz

DATE COMPLETED: 18-03-2004

LG/LID: Oneida/461

SOURCE(S): Abbott, Clifford, Oneida, 2000, Lincom Europa

1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

--small inventory of phonemes

--six V phonemes, two are nasal: /i/, /e/, /a/, /o/, nasals /ɰ/ and /u/

→ each V may occur in any of five varieties: short, lengthened, accented, simultaneously lengthened and accented, whispered

--four resonant Cs: /l/, /w/, /y/, /n/ → generally voiced, but shade to voiceless beside laryngeals and word-final position

--two oral stops: /t/, /k/ → voiced before any Vs or resonant Cs, voiceless anywhere else (this analysis views voicing of stops as noncontrastive, but other analyses differ, e.g. do ni:k 'how much', to ni:k 'that much' → the current analysis: to ni:k 'how much', tho ni:k 'that much' ⇒ the issue is, whether aspiration or voicing more prominent feature of contrast)

--single oral fricative /s/ (cf. voicing vs. aspiration like above); more variability among speakers:

→ for most speakers an /s/ between 2 Vs strongly voiced

an /s/ following of preceding /h/ = voiceless

elsewhere = intermediate amount of voicing

before /y/: /s/ → palatal fricative

--two laryngeal phonemes /ʔ/, /h/

--a palatal affricate, but it is understood as a cluster of phonemes: voiced → /tsy/ before Vs, /tsi/ before Cs; voiceless → /tshy/ before Vs, /tshi/ before C.

--no labials

--voicing not truly distinctive

--some restrictions on the clustering of Oneida phonemes:

→ sequences of 2 Vs, but not more than 2 Vs occur

→ C-clusters of up to five Cs are found

→ glottal stop occurs only after Vs, never after Cs

→ geminate Cs only with /t/ or /k/

→ /h/ occurs before or after Cs, but not both at the same time

→ word-initial clusters more restricted than word-medial ones

↳ no clusters with /h/ in word-initial position, except /sh/, /th/, /kh/

→ no resonant initial clusters in word-initial position except /ny/

→ clusters beginning with /k/, /t/, or /s/ may begin words except for /tl/ and /tt/

→ clusters of 3 Cs satisfy one of the following 4 conditions:

(a) end with a resonant; (b) begin with /ʔ/; (c) have /s/ between 2 oral stops; or (d)

have an oral stop between

two /s/s; in addition to the general condition (e) that a 3-C-cluster contain no

sequence of 2 Cs that does not

occur independently as a 2-C-cluster!

2. "Rules" Part 1

Epenthesis:

--combination of morphemes create a cluster of Cs that violate the phonotactics of the language → an epenthetic V is inserted, typically /e/

--four morpheme boundaries in which it may occur:

(i) between a verb stem and an aspectual morpheme (or a noun root and a nominal suffix) that is a glottal stop;

(ii) between a reflexive morpheme and a verb stem;

(iii) between a pronominal prefix and a verb stem (or between a possessive prefix and a noun stem);

(iv) between a pre-pronominal prefix and a pronominal prefix

--additional epenthetic processes:

→ in derivation of verb stems the separation of an incorporated noun and a verb often marked by V /a/ that belongs to neither morpheme → 'stem joiner'

→ in short words with not enough syllables for the accent placement rule, additional syllables created at front of word with a prothetic /i/

→ epenthesis that is part of the whispering process

Accent Morphophonemics:

--accent placement as a phonological process applies to words after the morphemes have been selected, arranged, and any needed epenthesis has applied

--the general rule is to count back two syllables (two Vs) from the end of the word and skip any stem joiners or epenthetic Vs before the aspect suffix (or nominal suffix)

--accent remains there, unless one of three special environments obtains:

→ if accent V immediately precedes a glottal stop, the glottal stop is deleted and the V is lengthened

→ if accent V immediately precedes a /h/ followed by a resonant C, /h/ is deleted and the V is lengthened

→ if accent V immediately precedes a single C (not a cluster) other than /h/, the V is lengthened and accent shifts to the following V

Whispering:

--many Oneida words have two different pronunciations depending on their occurrence in the sentence

--sentence-final forms (or words spoken in isolation or as citation forms) often undergo a process that includes whispering of the final syllable

--words with other words immediately after them do not undergo this process!

--exact process depends on phonological shape of the word:

→ most generic forms of the rule applies to words ending in a V or V + glottal stop these final syllables are whispered, including any /h/ that may occur before the V (e.g. sentence medial kanúhsoteʔ vs. sentence final kanúhsote 'house')

→ if the final syllable begins with a resonant and ends with a glottal stop, /h/ is inserted before the resonant and the whole

final syllable is whispered (e.g. kana:káleʔ vs. kana:káhle 'stick')

→ if the word ends in a C + a resonant + V, epenthetic V (/e/ if resonant is /l/ or /n/; /o/ if /w/; /i/ if /y/) is inserted after the

C and the rest of the word is whispered (kanákleʔ vs. kanákehle 'it dwells'; twítwe vs. tsítowe 'let's go'; sátyΛ / sáti 'sit')

→ if the next to last syllable contains a long accented V, length is converted to an /h/ and final syllable whispered

(nikayaʔtó:tΛ vs. nikayaʔtóhtΛ 'kind of body')

--this process somewhat fragile in current state of language

--for many speakers quite unconscious and automatic process; variation among speakers
 --also reanalyses of individual words, e.g. an epenthetic V in whispered form will be reanalyzed as part of the verb stem, or whispered form generalized as only form of the word, e.g. the epenthetic V in *kanákehle* reanalyzed as part of the verb stem for some speakers → *kanákehle* = sentence final form and *kanákele?* sentence medial

3. "Rules" Part 2

STRESS:

--five accentual patterns:

- (i) straight accent: one V carries heightened loudness and pitch (e.g. *-/á/*)
- (ii) long tone: one V is extra long (e.g. *-/á:/*)
- (iii) accent shift: one V is lengthened and the following V has heightened loudness and pitch (e.g. *-/a:tá/*)
- (iv) accent shift and long tone: one V is lengthened and the following V is both lengthened and has heightened loudness and pitch (e.g. *-/a:tá:/*)
- (v) final length: the last oral V in the word is lengthened but without change in pitch (*-/a:/*) → in this case typically an additional final syllable that has been either dropped or whispered due to a phonological process

4. Morphosyntax

VERB MORPHOLOGY

--sequence of four components: prepronominal prefixes + pronominal prefixes + verb stems + aspect suffixes

--all verbs have component *verb stem* → quite simple (sometimes single phoneme) or quite complex with many morphemes and layers of derivation

--aspectual component (with inflectional and some derivational possibilities)

--obligatory component of pronominal prefixes (agent, gender, patient, number, person)

--pre-pronominal prefix = set of eleven morphemes, up to five in a single word

--each component has rules for internal structure, for morphophonemic alternations at morpheme boundaries (and for alternations due to accent placement), and for co-occurrence restrictions with what may exist in the other components of the word

-pre-pronominal prefixes:

--future (Λ-), aorist (waʔ-), indefinite (a-) prefix coordinate with a particular suffix on verb stems (this suffix, the punctual, never occurs without one of the 3 prefixes, vice versa)

--aorist and indef. have multiple positions → depending on what other prefixes they occur with, may be discontinuous or have allomorphs in alternative positions

→ restrictions on multiple prefixes: mutually exclusive

(--pre-pronominal prefixes in their 163 combinations; see p. 13, 14)

--morphophonemics: in addition to the basic forms of these prefix clusters given in the chart there are alternates conditioned by the following pronominal component. The alternates are created by the following rules:

(i) epenthesis: when combining prepronominal and pronominal prefixes creates a C-cluster not allowed in Oneida, an epenthetic /e/ is inserted between the two components. In addition when a C-cluster includes prepronominal and pronominal prefixes and at least one C of a verb stem, then even if the cluster is otherwise allowed in the language, an epenthetic /e/ is still inserted between the two components.

(ii) glottal loss: if the basic form of a prepronominal component ends in glottal stop and the following pronominal component begins with either /h/ or /s/, then the glottal stop is deleted.

(iii) affricate: if the basic form of a prepronominal component ends in /s/ and the following pronominal component begins with /y/, then the /sy/ combination becomes /tsy/.

(iv) second person: when certain second person pronominal prefixes are used, they condition the following changes in the prepronominal prefixes: those that end in /a/ change the /a/ to /e/; those that end in /t/ change that /t/ to /ti/; and those that end in /s/ change the /s/ to /tsi/. there is some variation among speakers as to exactly which second person pronominal prefixes condition these changes, but the best generalization seems to be all the intransitive prefixes except the subjective singular.

(v) portmanteau: when the boundary between the prepronominal and pronominal prefixes contains the sequence /awa/ or /aʔwa/ or /waʔwa/, then that entire sequence is replaced by /u/.

(vi) accent: the normal rules of accent placement and laryngeal loss and prothesis will modify the prepronominal prefixes just as they would any other parts of an Oneida word. there is one additional change that occurs when the accent falls on the translocative prefix -ye- (or its combination with future -yΛ- or aorist -ya- or with other prefixes positioned in front of the translocative). in such cases the accented V doubles creating -yehé- (or -yΛhΛ- with the future or -yahá- with the aorist).

-pronominal prefixes:

--gender, 3 numbers, 3 persons (+exclusive/inclusive distinction), 2 semantic (or thematic) roles (agent/patient)

--base forms are heavily dependent on the beginning phoneme of the verb stem

→ general rule: whenever the pronominal prefix ends in a V and the verb stem begins in a V, the V of the verb stem is dropped

-verb stem:

--may be single morphemes (verb roots) or more complex derived forms built on a verb root through many layers of derivation

--verb stem components: reflexive + incorporated noun + verb root + derivational suffix

--reflexive:

→ semi-reflexive: basic form is -at-;

less common forms: -atΛ- before forms beginning with /n/ or /ʔ/

-ate- elsewhere, when epenthesis is needed

-an- before many forms beginning with /i/

-al- a few forms beginning with /a/

→ or full-reflexive: -atat-; this particular form is more inflectional than derivational and might be better analyzed as part of the pronominal prefix component

--incorporated noun:

→ noun roots (single noun morphemes),

→ nominalized verb stems (verb stems with a nominalization suffix), or

→ empty roots (semantically empty morphemes required by certain verbs when no specific noun is incorporated)

(i) noun roots are single morphemes; e.g. -nΛst- 'corn', -wil- 'offspring', -nuhs- 'building'

→ many nouns have an incorporated form that differs from their unincorporated form

(ii) nominalized verb stems can also be incorporated as nouns

→ verbs are nominalized by the suffixation of a nominalizer morpheme which has many

forms: -sl-, -asl-, -hsl-, -ahsl-, -tsl-, -atsl-, -ʔtsl-, -aʔtsl-, -ksl-, -aksl-, -aʔksl-, -ʔsl-, and -ʔt-

→ not strictly predictable which form used, but best generalization: -hsl- after Vs and forms with /t/ tend to occur after glottal stops; e.g. -atliyohsl- 'fighting' < -atliyo- 'fight'; -atΛloʔsl-

'friend' < *-atʌlo-* 'be friend'

(iii) empty morphemes usually a syllable or less

→ some verbs require that the noun incorporation slot be filled and when a more specific noun root or nominalized verb is not used, an empty morpheme fills the slot

→ the choice among many alternates depends on the incorporating verb stem

→ some examples: *-ʔsk-* in *-ʔsko-* 'put in water', or in *-ʔskut-* 'fry'

→ the meaning shift that the noun incorporation adds to the verb often is to specify a type of patient role but it is not always a predictable shift and is probably best viewed as a process of lexical derivation

→ presence and absence of an incorporated noun is controlled by the verb (the third component of the verb stem) where some verbs require noun incorporation, some verbs never allow it, and some provide a choice of incorporation or not

--verb root

→ third component of the verb stem

→ required slot for the verb root, although some derived verb stems are possible in this slot

→ can be single phonemes such as *-e-* 'go', or *-k-* 'eat', or more lengthy forms such as *-nuhwelatu-* 'thank'

--derivational suffixes

→ fourth component; may contain one or more of several derivational suffixes

--Verb Classes

(1) verb stems classified by their beginning phoneme; this determines many of the alternations in the forms of the pronominal prefixes; largest class = verb stems beginning with /a/ (a-stems), followed by i-, o-, u-stems, and e- and ʌ-stems; stems beginning with Cs = c-stems

(2) stems can be classified by limitations on the pronominal prefixes that are possible; most dynamic verb stems require subjective prefixes (except when the stative suffix is added), while others require objective prefixes (e.g. *-keʔtoht-* 'appear', *-yoʔte-* 'work'), while still others allow (or require) transitive prefixes; some stems take impersonal prefixes (e.g. intransitives such as *-lihʌ-* 'boil' or *-hli-* 'break') and stems that take only nonsingular prefixes (e.g. *-atʌlo-* 'be friends', *-aʔwʌtaʔ-* 'die off')

(3) verb stems classified by whether they treat some of the prepronominal prefixes as inflectional options or as lexical requirements; most inflectional prepronominal prefixes (future, aorist, indefinite, negative) not used as lexical requirements, but others are, with stems requiring the dualic being most common, followed by the cislocative, iterative, partitive, translocative, coincident, contrastive; for a few verb stems a combination of prefixes is required

(4) classifying verb stems by noun-incorporability. some verb stems require an incorporated noun, even a semantically empty one for the most general meaning; other verb stems never allow incorporation, e.g. *-anuhte-* 'know' does not incorporate while *-yʌtel-* 'know' does; others have suppletive forms for when there is no incorporated noun; there are also many verbs that offer speakers a choice between use with an incorporated noun (verbal derivation) and with an unincorporated noun (syntactic construction); one pattern in all this is that short verbs (single syllables or less) are very likely to incorporate nouns

(5) verbs have tendencies toward (or against) derivational suffixes and, though the boundaries may not be tight, it may be useful to classify verbs by their affinities for derivational suffixes; the verb root *-ohale-* 'wash', for example, quite freely incorporates nouns and derivational

suffixes

(6) finally it is useful to classify verbs by their aspectual requirements; there are three major classes - dynamic, stative, and motion verbs - with several subclasses, depending on the aspectual affix(es) they occur with

NOUN MORPHOLOGY

- four categories / noun types

- single morphemes: no internal structure; many animal names (*á:nuk* 'onion', *é:lhal* 'dog')

- root nouns: noun prefix (ka-, o-, or zero) + noun root + noun suffix (-aʔ/-eʔ)

- distinctive suffix, when root is incorporated into more complex constructions

- (but not used in simple noun forms)

- subclass: nouns referring to people → take pronominal suffix (verbs), e.g.

- latwaʔkánhaʔ* 'he's an Indian' < *atwaʔkánha* '(non-Iro.) individuum'

- deverbal nouns: formed by adding a nominalizer suffix to verb stems

- (a)sl- (after Cs), -(a)hsl- (after Vs), -tsl- (often after glottal stop), -a(ʔ)tsl-,

- and -ksl (infrequent)

- + regular noun suffix -aʔ or -iʔ to complete the word

- syntactic nouns: constructing a verb (typical with indefinite pronominal prefix + serial suffix), then simply using it syntactically as a noun (action verbs can be turned into actors or objects), e.g. *yekhu:niheʔ* 'cook' ('she cooks') (nouns for tools from verbs with instrumental suffix)

- possessive prefixes:

- a set of prefixes that occurs with the kind of nouns built directly from noun roots

- these prefixes similar to, but not the same as, the objective pronominal prefixes used on verbs

- they replace the noun prefixes (o-, ka-, and zero)

- when prefix ends in a V and the following stem begins in a V → the stem V is dropped

- noun suffixes

- with specialized meaning

- added to the kind of nouns built from noun roots (locative suffixes -ke after glottal stop, which means it is the typical choice after a regular noun suffix -aʔ and -hne anywhere else, external locative 'on'; -aku internal locative 'in' attaches directly to the noun root and replaces the regular noun suffix; -oku 'under' also attaches directly to a noun root;...)

- noun categories:

- natural history items

- for some plants and animals simple noun roots, e.g. *ohkwa:lí* 'bear', *oná:kʌt* 'ground hog'

- for many others the noun derives from a verbal description: *skʌhnáksʌ* 'fox' ('it has bad skin'), *tewahúhtes* 'hound dog' ('it has long ears')

- in most of these cases, however, the verb morphology is at least partially eclipsed:

- kohsa:tʌs* 'horse'

- small number of animal names formed from an atypical reduplicative pattern: *koskos* 'pig', *klikli* 'blue jay', *kitkit* 'chicken', *sliklik* 'cricket'

- nouns referring to land forms are either incorporated into a positional verb: *wéhkwayʌ* 'pond (lying)', *yohwé:noteʔ* 'island (standing)'; or have a locative suffix: *oska:wáku* '(in the brush)', *kanyatalá:ke* '(on the) lake'

--kinship terms tend to be verbs specifying the relationship they require to transitive (or in some cases plural) pronominal prefixes but they often drop the initial /y/ or /w/ of the prefix: *aksótha?* 'she is grandparent to me', 'my grandmother'; *laksótha?* 'he is grandparent to me', 'my grandfather', *aknullhá* 'she is mother to me', 'my mother'

--body parts are noun roots that usually require locative suffix and a subjective pronominal prefix for the possessor; an objective pronominal prefix is seen as a counter to the inalienable possession of body parts: *knutsí:ne* 'my head' from *-nutsi-* *kkahlá:ke* 'my eye' from *-kahl-*

--nouns for human beings tend to be either single noun roots, most of which have subjective pronominal prefixes, or action verbs in a habitual aspect: *lu:kwé* 'he's a person', *yu:kwé* 'she's a person', *lato:láts* 'he's a hunter'

--color terms are simple noun roots that may incorporate in a few specialized verbs; color terms themselves are usually followed by a classifier expression *niwahsohkó:tΛ* 'that kind of color': *otsí:nkwál* 'yellow', *olú:ya* 'blue'

--number terms are usually single morphemes; counting is based on 10 and makes use of a special morpheme *yawΛ:lé* for '-teen' and a verb *-ahsΛ-* for multiples of ten: *úskah* 'one', *wisk* 'five', *oye:lí* 'ten', *úskah yawΛ:lé* 'eleven', *wisk niwáhsΛ* 'fifty'

--for tools a small number are built from noun roots, but most are descriptions built from the verb morphology with the instrumental suffix: *u:ták* 'pail', *kaná:tsi?* 'bucket', *yehnekataliha?tákhwa?* 'tea kettle' ('one heats water with it')

--abstractions tend to be verbs with a nominalizer suffix: *atehΛsla?* 'shame' from *-atehΛ-* 'be ashamed', *atunhétsla?* 'spirit' from *-unhe-* 'live'

PRONOUNS

--most of the pronoun work done with pronominal prefix in the verb

--but there are some independent pronouns (used for particular emphasis or contrast/unmarked number):

1.p. *ni*; *ni?*í, *i*

2.p. *ni:sé*, *ni?*í:sé; *i:sé*

3.p. *ne*

PARTICLES

--all words in the language not have any internal complexity (single morphemes); or might be defined in functional terms: all words that function as neither nouns nor verbs (both definitions are too restrictive)

→ all single morpheme words not used as nouns are particles: *tho* 'there, then', *tsi?* 'as, that', *she:kú* 'still', *ostúha* 'little bit'

--also some frozen verb forms that have developed special senses (these verb forms are either partially decayed or quite transparent): *niyo:lé* 'a distance', *ni:yót* 'how it appears', *ΛyólhΛne?* 'tomorrow', *swatye:lΛ* 'sometimes', *tyótkut* 'always'

--some combinations of particles have melded → idiomatic meaning: *nok* 'only' from *ne ok*; *okhale?* 'and' from *ok ale?*; *okhna?* 'and then' from *ok na?*

--other combinations not melded but developed semantic specializations: *onΛ kwi* 'now then'; *kwah i:kΛ* 'very'; *nok tsi?* 'but'; *ok ne?n* 'or' *ki?* *wah* 'indeed'

--other combinations can contain quite a few particles (often used to introduce sentences or clauses): *onΛ kiʔ aleʔ wi* 'immediately'; *kwah kΛs katiʔ wi* 'usually'

--several particles are exceptions to the accent placement and accent shift rules of the phonology and longer combinations of particles have their own idiosyncratic accent patterns

--some particles required by particular verb or noun constructions → almost part of the morphology of these words